

FEATURES OF THE DIFFERENTIATION METHOD, CARRIED OUT ON THE BASIS OF IDENTICAL TASKS

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Annotation:

This article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of the differentiation method, carried out on the basis of the same tasks. The peculiarities of this method are that all students are offered tasks of the same content, but an individual approach is provided in the process of their completion. Some students have the opportunity to complete the task independently, while others carry out the work under the guidance of the teacher. The advantages of this method include the creation of equal opportunities in education, increasing student activity, overcoming individual difficulties, and effectively organizing the educational process. The article also provides an example of the phased organization of educational activities for the practical application of this method. Analysis shows that differentiation through similar tasks is one of the effective learning strategies, allowing for the consolidation of knowledge and skills, taking into account the individual capabilities of students.

Аннотация:

Мазкур мақолада бир хил топшириқлар асосида амалга ошириладиган дифференциация усулининг назарий ва амалий жиҳатлари таҳлил

қилинган. Бу усулнинг ўзига хос томонлари шундаки, барча ўқувчиларга бир хил мазмундаги топшириқлар таклиф этилади, аммо уларнинг бажарилиши жараёнида индивидуал ёндашув таъминланади. Айрим таълим олувчилар топшириқни мустақил равишда бажариш имконига эга бўлса, бошқалари ўқитувчи раҳбарлигида ишни амалга оширадilar. Ушбу усулнинг афзалликлари сифатида таълимда тенг имкониятлар яратилиши, ўқувчиларнинг фаоллигини ошириш, индивидуал қийинчиликларни енгиш ва таълим жараёнини самарали ташкил этиш каби жиҳатлар кўрсатилган. Мақолада, шунингдек, ушбу усулнинг амалий татбиқ этилиши учун босқичма-босқич ўқув фаолиятини ташкил этиш намунаси келтирилган. Таҳлиллар шуни кўрсатмоқдаки, бир хил топшириқлар орқали фарқлаш самарали таълим стратегияларидан бири бўлиб, ўқувчиларнинг индивидуал имкониятларини ҳисобга олган ҳолда билим ва кўникмаларни мустаҳкамлаш имконини беради.

Аннотация:

В данной статье анализируются теоретические и практические аспекты метода дифференциации, реализуемого на основе одинаковых заданий. Особенности этого метода заключаются в том, что всем учащимся предлагаются задания одинакового содержания, но в процессе их выполнения обеспечивается индивидуальный подход. Некоторые учащиеся имеют возможность выполнить задание самостоятельно, в то время как другие работают под руководством преподавателя. Преимуществами этого метода являются создание равных возможностей в образовании, повышение активности учащихся, преодоление индивидуальных трудностей и эффективная организация образовательного процесса. В статье также приводится пример поэтапной организации учебной деятельности для практического применения данного метода. Анализ показывает, что дифференциация посредством одинаковых заданий является одной из эффективных стратегий обучения, позволяющей закрепить знания и навыки с учетом индивидуальных возможностей учащихся.

In this differentiation method, the tasks will be the same in content for all students. That is, members of the training group at different levels are given tasks of the same type. In these conditions, some students complete tasks under

the teacher's guidance, while others complete them independently. Such an approach creates certain conveniences for teachers and students and has a number of pedagogical advantages in the organization of educational activities.

In the process of mastering new educational material, the teacher often prefers to use a frontal (i.e., general for the entire group) form of work. In this form, as a rule, students with high preparedness are actively involved, while students with a lower level of knowledge play the role of observers and listeners. Therefore, in this case, the effectiveness of the educational process may limit the possibilities of the teacher's individual approach. However, this method can yield positive results in the development of students' knowledge and skills by involving all students in unified pedagogical tasks [2].

Students with strong preparation are usually distinguished by their ability to give reasoned and correct answers to questions, reason, clearly express their thoughts, and logically justify their actions. In such situations, the teacher may have a subjective impression that all students have fully mastered the material. However, practice shows that students with a low level of knowledge and competencies often participate passively in this process and experience difficulties in analyzing tasks. In many cases, they may not be able to fully receive the necessary assistance from the teacher and may encounter problems in responding with independent thinking [1].

Low-prepared students, in general, although they are somewhat prepared for independent work, in many cases feel the need for the teacher's help in fully understanding and solving tasks. Therefore, by differentiating students according to the degree of independence, it is possible to reduce shortcomings in the educational process. In this method, high-ability students can start working independently and additional tasks can be prepared for them, while the teacher focuses mainly on less prepared students.

This method allows for more active involvement of weaker students in the learning process, developing their abilities to understand and analyze the material. The learning process begins at an approximate stage, during which all learners familiarize themselves with the task and try to understand its content, purpose, and rules of execution. After this, some students begin independent work, while the rest, under the teacher's guidance, partially complete the task and analyze it, working on examples. This creates a psychological and cognitive foundation for their subsequent transition to independent work [3].

This approach serves to create equal opportunities in education, activate all students, and ensure a personalized approach. Thus, it becomes possible to

increase the effectiveness of general education and the level of assimilation of students.

Schoolchildren who encounter difficulties in the learning process complete all assignments under the guidance of the teacher and with methodological assistance. Students determine at what stage they should move on to performing the task independently, based on their level of preparedness, understanding, and confidence. At the same time, students have the opportunity to return to the teacher's guidance at any stage if necessary, which ensures psychological safety and an individual approach to the educational process [4].

When organizing work based on cards, it is advisable to use the following step-by-step model:

1. First stage - introduction and selection: at this stage, students familiarize themselves with the text of the assignment. Among those who understand the content, a certain part prefers to engage in independent work. These students may be offered additional tasks on the studied material, for example, conducting a comparative analysis of opposite properties.

2. The second stage is analysis and orientation: at this stage, under the guidance of the teacher, the content of the task is analyzed, the content of the studied patterns is highlighted together with the students, and work directions are determined. Through this process, other students also prepare for independent work.

3. The third stage is the search for a solution and drawing a conclusion: at this stage, creative thinking is carried out under the guidance of the teacher on the solution of the task. After this, part of the students independently formulate conclusions on the task, and the rest perform this work in cooperation with the teacher.

4. The fourth stage - control and reflection: students who have begun independent work will have the opportunity to check, evaluate, and analyze their work. This stage serves to strengthen independence and characterize the acquired knowledge.

Such a step-by-step approach serves the gradual and active involvement of students in the educational process, taking into account their individual capabilities, the formation of independent thinking and critical analysis skills.

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